

Robust optical frequency dissemination with a dual-polarization coherent receiver

Technical Note: Open Hardware

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Abstract

The purpose of this document is to describe some “open-hardware” aspects of the demonstrations related to a robust optical frequency dissemination with a dual-polarization coherent receiver.

1. Introduction: Coherent Detection

A simple photodiode is not an optimal choice for the coherent-detection of an optical signal affected by polarization changes, as it is prone to impairments such as PIPN and beatnote fading. It can be reliably exploited only for non-coherent direct detection techniques where the information is encoded in the signal intensity. Usually, coherent receiving in optical transmission is accomplished by polarization diversity receivers. These are based on devices referred to as Optical Hybrids because they combine optoelectronics element such as photodiodes and electronic front-ends with optical elements such as beam-splitters (BS).

Coherent receiving techniques are exploited to detect the phase difference between a local oscillator (LO) and a received signal (RX). Considering figure (2.3), LO is represented by the regeneration laser whereas RX is represented by Eout0 that is now rewritten for convenience as $e^{j(\omega_L t + \phi_{RX}(t))}$ explicating the angular frequency of the laser source ω_L that is considered constant in time and the phase term ϕ_{RX} that includes the time-dependent phase noise. Similarly the regeneration laser has the form

The phase difference is extracted by measuring the beatnote of the two optical fields on a photodiode. This device is an inversely-biased pn junction which produces a current proportional to the incident optical power. The proportionality factor is the responsivity $R(\lambda)$ which is defined as the ratio of the generated photocurrent I_p to the incident radiant power P_i . I_p depends on the number of incident photons, weighted by the conversion coefficient $\eta(\lambda)$ called quantum efficiency. $\eta(\lambda)$ vanishes for wavelengths higher than a cutoff value above which the energy of the absorbed photon is lower than the band gap, thus insufficient for generating electron-hole pairs; $\eta(\lambda)$ also decreases for too high photon energy due to

recombination effects; therefore $\eta(\lambda)$ is markedly bigger from zero only in a spectral window of a certain width which depends on the junction material and doping. For instance Si photodiodes have high efficiency in the 500nm- 800nm window while Ge photodiodes have high efficiency in the 1000nm- 1500nm range. The expression of the responsivity is thus:

$$(1) \quad R(\lambda) = \frac{I_p}{P_i} = \frac{e\eta(\lambda) \frac{P_i}{h\nu}}{P_i} = \frac{e\eta(\lambda)\lambda}{hc}$$

where e is the electron charge and h is the Planck's constant. Another parameter of interest of a photodiode is the bandwidth which varies on the reverse voltage applied (which modifies the junction capacitance), the internal shunt resistance and other construction characteristics. As an example, the photodiode Hamamatsu G9801 used in this work is a InGaAs PIN junction with a working window centered at 1.4 μ m, responsivity of 0.9A/W and 2 GHz bandwidth.

Considering the two electromagnetic waves to be mixed, and , the photocurrent generated in a number of periods T of the optical field (usually this is a large number, since T is in the range of few fs) is therefore:

$$(2) \quad I_p = R \cdot P_i \propto R \cdot \langle |E'_{RX} + E'_{LO}|^2 \rangle$$

where the average optical power is:

$$(3) \quad \begin{aligned} \langle |E'_{RX} + E'_{LO}|^2 \rangle &= \frac{1}{T} \int_T |E'_{RX} + E'_{LO}|^2 dt = \\ &= \frac{1}{T} \int_T [E_{RX}^2 \cos^2(\omega_L t + \phi_{RX}) + E_{LO}^2 \cos^2(\omega_L t + \phi_{LO}) + \\ &\quad + 2E_{RX} E_{LO} \cos(\omega_L t + \phi_{RX}) \cos(\omega_L t + \phi_{LO})] dt \\ &= \left[\frac{E_{RX}^2}{2} + \frac{E_{LO}^2}{2} + E_{RX} E_{LO} \cos(\omega_I t + \Delta\phi) \right] \end{aligned}$$

with $\Delta\phi = \phi_{RX} - \phi_{LO}$ $\omega_I = \omega_L - \omega_{LO}$

The obtained result contains dc components proportional to the optical power of the two fields, and an ac component, oscillating at the difference frequency ω_I of the two optical fields. This latter term also contains the time-varying relative phase-fluctuations between the

two carriers, which is the information of interest in coherent optical detection. In some applications, the balanced detection configuration is exploited to directly filter out the dc term [87]. This is sketched in figure (2.4(a)): a special 3 dB optical splitter halves the two incoming fields and adds a π phase shift to either the signal RX or LO so that two fields are produced: the sum and the difference .

Injecting the two outputs in two series connected photodiodes gives a current flowing in the output branch I_{out} equal to the difference:

$$(4) \quad I_{out} = \frac{R}{2} \cdot [\langle |E'_{RX} + E'_{LO}|^2 \rangle - \langle |E'_{RX} - E'_{LO}|^2 \rangle] = R E_{RX} E_{LO} [\cos(\Delta\phi)]$$

that shows that the terms dependent on the power are absent.

The detection procedure contributes to the phase noise affecting the received signal with a component Φ_{det} which includes the noise introduced by photodetectors and the readout electronics. The main noise source for a photodetector is the shot noise which has Poissonian distribution and is associated to the quantization of the flux of electrons flowing in the photodiode. Both the photocurrent generated by the optical signal (in particular, both the ac and dc terms) and the dark current of the photodiode, a parasitic phenomenon caused by leakage paths in the junction and independent on the illuminance power, contribute to it; however, the dominant term is usually due to the dc photogenerated current. The shot-noise-induced current PSD is proportional to the sum of the two terms and has the expression [88]: $S(f) \propto q (i_{AVG} + i_D) |H(f)|^2$ where i_{AVG} is the average photocurrent, i_D is the dark current and $H(f)$ is the Fourier transform of the impulse response of the electron-hole recombination which can be approximated with $H(f) \approx 1$ at the Fourier frequencies of interest in this work, i.e. for $f < 1\text{MHz}$.

a) Scheme of a balanced photodetector: S1 is a 3 dB splitter which delays ELO by π phase shift. The output is the difference of the two photocurrents

(b) Electronic readout of the photocurrent: schematic of transimpedance amplifier (TIA) with some typical values of the components [89]

Figure 1: Two common solutions adopted in optical coherent receiving

The electronic readout of the photocurrent is usually accomplished by a transimpedance amplifier (TIA) that is shown in figure (2.4(b)). Basically, the TIA generates an output voltage $V_{out} = -I_{pd} \cdot R_f$ where R_f is the feedback resistance. The electronic amplification can introduce additional noise generated by the random thermal motion of electrons into the R_f (Johnson noise). Its value should thus be high enough to ensure an efficient current/voltage conversion, but low enough that the Johnson noise contribution is negligible. In practice, loads in the range 1-100 kΩ are adopted; in this case the Johnson noise is always negligible with respect to shot noise for typical optical powers available at detection, in the μW -mW range.

2. Multi-channel coherent detection

A simple photodiode is not an optimal choice for the coherent-detection of an optical signal affected by polarization changes, as it is prone to impairments such as PIPN and beatnote fading. It can be reliably exploited only for non-coherent direct detection techniques where the information is encoded in the signal intensity. Usually, coherent receiving in optical transmission is accomplished by *polarization diversity* receivers. These are based on devices referred to as *Optical Hybrids* because they combine optoelectronics element such

as photodiodes and electronic front-ends with optical elements such as beam-splitters (BS), retarders and so on.

The basic Optical Hybrid is the six port 2×4 90° that is shown in figure (3.1). The two input ports accept two linearly polarized and aligned fields. This reduces the treatment

to a one-dimension problem. We express the fields using the complex notation, as:

$$(5) \quad E'_S = E_S e^{j(\omega_S t + \phi_S)} \quad E'_{LO} = E_{LO} e^{j(\omega_{LO} t + \phi_{LO})}$$

In addition, one branch of either E'_S or E'_{LO} (E'_{LO} in picture 3.1) is phase retarded by $\frac{\pi}{2}$ which corresponds in complex notation to a multiplication by a factor j . This is achieved by introducing a proper retarder plate that modifies the relative OPL of the beam. Then E'_S is combined with E'_{LO} on splitter S3 and their interference is revealed on a balanced detector giving I_P ; similarly E'_S and jE'_{LO} are combined by splitter S4 and their interference is revealed on a second balanced detector giving I_Q . Considering the scheme of the balanced detector in figure (2.4), it follows:

$$(6) \quad \begin{aligned} E_{P1} &= \frac{1}{2} (E'_S + E'_{LO}) & E_{P2} &= \frac{1}{2} (E'_S - E'_{LO}) \\ E_{Q1} &= \frac{1}{2} (E'_S + j E'_{LO}) & E_{Q2} &= \frac{1}{2} (E'_S - j E'_{LO}) \end{aligned}$$

Figure 2: 2×4 90° Optical Hybrid. A phase shift of $\frac{\pi}{2}$ is introduced by a proper retarding plate. S1, S2: 3dB splitters. S3, S4: balanced detectors splitters (see figure (2.4(a)))

and the corresponding output photocurrents, considering formula (2.19), are:

$$(7) \quad \begin{aligned} I_P &= \frac{R}{2} E_{LO} E_S [\omega_I t + \cos(\Delta\phi)] \\ I_Q &= \frac{R}{2} E_{LO} E_S [\omega_I t + \sin(\Delta\phi)] \end{aligned}$$

where R is the responsivity of the photodiode, $\Delta\phi$ indicates as usual the interference term ($\phi_S - \phi_{LO}$) and $\omega_I = \omega_S - \omega_{LO}$ is the heterodyne angular frequency. Therefore if the amplitude of the local oscillator is considered constant, a 2×4 90° Optical Hybrid is actually able to reveal a couple of signals proportional respectively to the real part and the imaginary part of the incoming field E'_S . For this reason, it is usually referred to as phase-diversity receiver.

The optoelectronic device which allows the polarization diversity detection is called *dualpolarization Optical Hybrid receiver* (DPOH) and is sketched in figure (3.2). The incoming field is split by means of a polarizing beam splitter (PBS) that reflects the component of the electric field polarized parallel to the plane of the diagonal face (\hat{y} in the figure) and transmits the other component (\hat{x} in the figure). The local field \vec{E}_{LO} is linearly polarized at 45° with respect the reference frame $\{\hat{x}, \hat{y}\}$ and is split into two by a non-polarizing beam splitter S1. The four components are then combined into two 2×4 90° Optical Hybrids whose output currents are further amplified by four integrated transimpedance amplifiers (TIA). All these hardware components constitute the so-called *optical front-end* of the receiver.

Analytically, we consider the two fields in the form:

$$(8) \quad \vec{E}_S = \begin{bmatrix} E_{SX} \\ E_{SY} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} |E_{SX}| e^{j\phi_X} \\ |E_{SY}| e^{j\phi_Y} \end{bmatrix} e^{j(\omega_S t + \phi_S)} \quad \vec{E}_{LO} = \sqrt{2} \begin{bmatrix} E_{LO} \\ E_{LO} \end{bmatrix} e^{j(\omega_{LO} t + \phi_{LO})}$$

Note that the module of the local oscillator is set $|\vec{E}_{LO}| = 2$ for convenience in the calculations. Developing formula (3.3) for all four branches we obtain the expression of the four currents. For the sake of clarity, the time dependence is here explicit:

$$\begin{aligned}
 I_{xP}(t) &= \frac{R}{2} |E_{LO}(t)| |E_{sX}(t)| \cos(\omega_I t + \Delta\phi_X(t)) = \mathbf{Re}(E_{sX}^*(t) E_{LO}(t)) \\
 I_{xQ}(t) &= \frac{R}{2} |E_{LO}(t)| |E_{sX}(t)| \sin(\omega_I t + \Delta\phi_X(t)) = \mathbf{Im}(E_{sX}^*(t) E_{LO}(t)) \\
 I_{yQ}(t) &= \frac{R}{2} |E_{LO}(t)| |E_{sY}(t)| \sin(\omega_I t + \Delta\phi_Y(t)) = \mathbf{Im}(E_{sY}^*(t) E_{LO}(t)) \\
 I_{yP}(t) &= \frac{R}{2} |E_{LO}(t)| |E_{sY}(t)| \cos(\omega_I t + \Delta\phi_Y(t)) = \mathbf{Re}(E_{sY}^*(t) E_{LO}(t))
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{9}$$

Figure 3: Block diagram of an polarization diversity optical receiving. The dashed line encloses the optical front-end of a dual-polarization optical hybrid (DPOH). PBS: polarizing beam-splitter S1: 3dB splitter. TIA: transimpedance amplifier. ADC: analog-to-digital converter. DSP: digital signal processing

where $\Delta\phi_X(t) = \phi_X(t) - \phi_{LO}(t)$ and $\Delta\phi_Y(t) = \phi_Y(t) - \phi_{LO}(t)$. In the last equalities the exponential form is used for a more compact notation.

The crucial improvement of this device as compared to a phase-diversity receiver is represented in this set of equations and is the overcoming of the intensity fading. Thanks to the proper orientation set for \vec{E}_{LO} , an output signal is always revealed, at least on one branch, for every polarization orientation assumed by \vec{E}_s . This is a fundamental requirement to ensure a continuous tracking of the optical phase.

A second important observation is that the four photocurrents are functions of the input polarization parameters, of the fiber birefringence and of the metrological phase modeling of the DPOH outputs. Even though the photocurrents depend on non-trivial functions (as shown in equation (2.35)), we will show that it is possible to extract the desired phase information.

2.1 Channels Formulas

The scope of this section is to transpose the mathematical model adopted for the optical fiber as stated in equation (2.29) into the channels formulas (3.5) of the DPOH. In order to perform this calculation, some hypotheses are assumed:

- the reference frame for the polarization against which the launched field is defined, is the same of the DPOH.
- LO is linearly polarized at $\frac{\pi}{4}$ inclination with respect to the PBS of the DPOH and with a phase assumed equal for both components. This configuration is achieved connecting the regeneration laser source to the DPOH via PM optical elements.
- we stress that the parameter of isotropic phase $\Delta\Phi$ of the fiber Jones Matrix (see section (2.3.1)) is considered for simplicity included in the metrological phase φ of the arriving signal at the remote link end. In fact the purpose of the present DSP is to extract the PIPN from the metrological phase φ of the received field, containing both the original laser phase and the isotropic contribution of the optical fiber $\Delta\Phi$, which is common for the two polarization components.

In addition, the values of the components of E_{LO} can be assumed equal to one, for simplicity. The polarization state of the launched field is assumed right-hand circular; the channels formula can thus be obtained applying the formulas (3.5) to the field arriving at the remote end E_{out} expressed by (2.37) and (2.38):

$$I_{xP}(t) \propto \mathbf{Re}(E_{\text{outx}}) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \left[\cos(\theta) \sin\left(\frac{\delta}{2} + \theta - \phi\right) - \sin(\theta) \cos\left(\frac{\delta}{2} - \theta + \phi\right) \right] \quad (10)$$

$$I_{xQ}(t) \propto \mathbf{Im}(E_{\text{outx}}) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \left[\cos\left(\frac{\delta}{2}\right) \cos(\phi) - \sin\left(\frac{\delta}{2}\right) \sin(2\theta - \phi) \right] \quad (11)$$

$$I_{yP}(t) \propto \mathbf{Re}(E_{\text{outy}}) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \left[\sin\left(\frac{\delta}{2}\right) \sin(2\theta - \phi) + \cos\left(\frac{\delta}{2}\right) \cos(\phi) \right] \quad (12)$$

$$I_{yQ}(t) \propto \mathbf{Im}(E_{\text{outy}}) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \left[\sin\left(\frac{\delta}{2}\right) \cos(2\theta - \phi) + \cos\left(\frac{\delta}{2}\right) \sin(\phi) \right] \quad (13)$$

It should be noted that the oscillating term at angular frequency ω_l has been neglected, as it has been assumed that the heterodyne beatnotes detected at the DPOH outputs can be downconverted to dc using an analog mixer or its DSP analogue. The obtained equations depend on both the parameters δ and θ which represents the birefringence of the fiber and the parameter ϕ which is the metrological phase.

It can be useful to calculate the set of equations (3.6-3.9) for some particular case of δ and θ .

- if $\delta = \theta = 0$ we get:

$$\begin{aligned} I_{xP}(t) &= \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} [-\sin(\phi)] = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \left[\cos\left(\phi + \frac{\pi}{2}\right) \right] \\ I_{xQ}(t) &= \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} [\cos(\phi)] = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \left[\sin\left(\phi + \frac{\pi}{2}\right) \right] \\ I_{yP}(t) &= \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} [\cos(\phi)] \\ I_{yQ}(t) &= \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} [\sin(\phi)] \end{aligned}$$

which means that the optical fiber has not birefringence effect, as expected

- supposing that at instant k we are in the undisturbed case and at instant $k+1$ the fiber behaves like a quarter-wave on-axis, namely with $\theta = 0$ and $\delta = \frac{\pi}{2}$, then:

$$\begin{aligned} I_{xP} &= \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} (1) \sin\left(\frac{\pi}{4} + 0 - \phi\right) - (0) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \cos\left(\phi + \frac{\pi}{4}\right) \\ I_{xQ} &= \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \cos\left(\frac{\pi}{4}\right) \cos(\phi) - \sin\left(\frac{\pi}{4}\right) \sin(-\phi) = \dots = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \sin\left(\phi + \frac{\pi}{4}\right) \\ I_{yP} &= \dots = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \cos\left(\phi + \frac{\pi}{4}\right) \\ I_{yQ} &= \dots = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}} \sin\left(\phi + \frac{\pi}{4}\right) \end{aligned}$$

which means that the polarization is linear, as expected.

Interestingly, it can be observed that the set of equations (3.6-3.9) shows an asymmetry, namely the two couple of equations for the two axes are not specular. It can be shown that this fact simply arises from the arbitrary choices of the signs of circularity and of the Jones retarder matrix $M(\bar{\delta})$ adopted in the calculations.

Since the photocurrents modeled by equations (3.6-3.9) are measured continuously, it may look natural to invert the system in order to obtain an expression of φ , which is the information we are interested in. It must however be noted that the system is not linear and its variables δ, θ, φ are not mathematical entities but are experimental data i.e. affected by uncertainty, therefore a straightforward inversion is not possible. The method adopted in this thesis to overcome the problem is described in the following section.

3. Evaluation board for Intradyne Coherent Receiver (ICR)

In this paragraph we describe some concept design and usage of evaluation board for Intradyne Coherent Receiver (ICR) of Neophotonics (Neophotonics MICRO-IC) used in [1]. Complete products by Neophotonics will exploit all the possibilities offered by this hardware. The designed ICR is a coherent receiver with three PM fiber inputs corresponding to Signal X-Polarization, Signal Y-Polarization and Local Oscillator (LO). The output of the receiver is designed as coplanar RF pins for 4 differential channels corresponding to the two polarizations.

The electrical bias to the photodiodes (PDs) and Trans-Impedance-Amplifiers (TIAs) is provided through DC pins on the ICR module which are terminated in six DB15HD female connectors on the test board. These connectors also provide monitoring of PD photocurrent, input to the controls for TIA operation, AGC or MC mode selection and gain settings, as well as peak detect voltage from TIA. The pin assignment details of these DB15HD connectors are shown in the Table1 below. The TIA output can be disabled with a bias on the SHD pin as defined in the Table 2 below.

The DC bias to eight PDs and measurement of photocurrent is provided thru the connectors P3 and P4 (Table 1). These bias lines are independently paired with ground at connectors

so that separate power supplies can be used for independent bias control. The bias input to each of the eight PDs (P3-15, 14, 13, 12 and P4-11, 12, 13 and 14) is routed via individual 100 Ohm resistor (R9 to R16). Voltage across this resistor (at P3-4, 3, 2, 1 and P4-7, 8, 9 and 10) is a measure of the photocurrent on individual photodiode.

Table 1: DC Pin Assignment for ICR Module & Test Board

		FIBER INPUT SIDE							
	Board PIN #	Description	Symbol	PKG Pin #	Symbol	Description	Board PIN #		
P1 DB15F	5	Shut Down Y	SHD Y	1	40	DNU	Do Not Use	6	
	15	GND	GND		39	PKD-XQ	Peak Detect XQ	11	
	10	Peak Detector YI	PKD-YI	2		GND	GND	1	
	4	GND	GND		38	GC-XQ	Gain Control XQ	7	
	14	Gain Control YI	GC-YI	3		GND	Ground	12	
	9	GND	GND		37	OA-XQ	Output adjust XQ	2	
	3	Output Amplitude YI	OA - YI	4		GND	Ground	8	
	13	GND	GND		36	DNU	Do Not Use	13	
	8	Do Not Use	DNU	5	35	MC X	Manual Control X	3	
	2	Do Not Use	DNU	6		GND	GND	9	
	12	TIA Bias - YI	VCC - YI	7	34	VCC - XQ	TIA Bias - XQ	14	
	7	GND	GND	8	33	GND	GND	4	
	1							10	
	11							15	
6							5		
P3 DB15F	5	GND	GND			GND	Ground	6	
	15	PD Bias - YI-A	VPD-YI-A	9	32	VPD-XQ-D	PD Bias - XQ-D	11	
	10	Measure PD	MPD-YI-A			MPD-XQ-D	Measure PD	1	
	4	GND	GND			GND	Ground	7	
	14	PD Bias YI - B	VPD-YI-B	10	31	VPD-XQ-C	PD Bias - XQ-C	12	
	9	Measure PD	MPD-YI-B			MPD-XQ-C	Measure PD	2	
	3	GND	GND			GND	Ground	8	
	13	PD Bias - YQ-C	VPD-YQ-C	11	30	VPD-XI-B	PD Bias - XI-B	13	
	8	Measure PD	MPD-YO-C			MPD-XI-B	Measure PD	3	
	2	GND	GND			GND	Ground	9	

	12	PD Bias - YQ-D	VPD-YQ-D	12	29	VPD-XI-A	PD Bias - XI-A	14	
	7	Measure PD	MPD-YQ-D			MPD-XI-A	Measure PD	4	
	1	GND	GND			GND	Ground	10	
	11							15	
	6							5	
P5 DB15F	5	GND	GND	13	28	GND	GND	6	P6 DB15F
	15	TIA Bias - YQ	VCC - YQ	14	27	VCC	TIA Bias - XI	11	
	10	GND	GND		26	DNU	Do Not Use	1	
	4	Manual Control Y	MC - Y	15	25	DNU	Do Not Use	7	
	14	DNU	DNU	16	24	OA - XI	Output adjust XI	12	
	9	Ground	GND			GND	GND	2	
	3	Output Amplitude YQ	OA - YQ	17	23	GC - XI	Gain Control XI	8	
	13	GND	GND			GND	GND	13	
	8	Gain Control YQ	GC - YQ	18	22	PKD - XI	Peak Detect XI	3	
	2	Ground	GND			GND	GND	9	
	12	Peak Detect YQ	PKD-YQ	19		GND	GND	14	
	7	Do Not Use	DNU	20	21	SHD X	Shut Down X	4	
	1							10	
	11							15	
	6							5	
RF PIN OUTPUT									

All four TIA inputs and outputs are terminated in DB15HD connectors P1, P2, P5 and P6. Connectors P1 and P5 control the TIAs for Y polarization and connectors P2 and P6 control TIAs for X Polarization. All four TIAs have separate Bias lines (P1-12, P2-14, P5-15, and P6-11) on the test board and can be controlled independently. The TIA can be used either in MC (Manual Control) or AGC (Auto Gain Control) mode. The two pins (P5-4 and P2-3) require bias to switch from one mode to another. For a bias between 0 to 0.8V TIAs operate in MC mode. For the AGC mode these two pins require an input between 2 volts and V_{cc} .

The control lines (P1-14, P2-7, P5-8 and P6-8) for the four TIAs provide a means to control TIA gain in the MC mode. The input to the gain control lines have to be in the range of 0 to V_{cc} volts.

In the AGC mode, the amplitude of the output voltage for each TIA can be selected by a voltage on the V_{OA} ('Output Amplitude') pins (P1-3, P2-2, P5-3 and P6-12). The range of voltage on the pin can be 0.5 V to 2.0 V volts.

Table 2 Turn-On Bias and Control Voltages

Parameter	Symbol	Voltage Range			Unit
		Min	Typ	Max	
PD Bias	VPD	4.5	5.0	5.5	V
TIA Bias	V _{cc}	3.15	3.3	3.45	V
TIA Current (each)	ICC			70	mA
Output Amplitude Control for AGC Mode	VOA	0.5		2.0	V
Total Power Dissipation				1	W
Mode Selection : MC Mode AGC Mode	VMC	0 2.0		0.8 V _{cc}	V
Gain Control	VGC	0		V _{cc}	V
Shut Down (SHD) : Disable Enable	SHD	2 0		V _{cc} 0.8	V

The four channel differential RF outputs for the ICR package are implemented in 20 coplanar pins in the GSGSG configuration. These RF signals are carried by the coplanar lines (CPW lines) to the GPPO (MSMP) male card edge connectors. Coaxial RF cables with GPPO (or MSMP)-female connectors can be used to evaluate the RF performance of ICR module.

Table 3: RF Pin assignment for ICR Package & Test Board

RF Pins	Function
1	GND
2	XI-p
3	GND
4	XI-n
5	GND
6	
7	XQ-p
8	GND

9	XQ-n
10	GND
11	
12	YI-p
13	GND
14	YI-n
15	GND
16	
17	YQ-p
18	GND
19	YQ-n
20	GND

A certain power up and power down sequence needs to be followed to avoid damaging the active components in the ICR unit. All the DC input pins from the test board should be connected to appropriate power supplies. The RF outputs should be terminated into 50 Ohms terminations or test equipment with 50 ohm terminations.

The unit should be powered up, this sequence should be used:

After connecting the bias and control leads to appropriate supplies follow the power up sequence as defined here to avoid damaging the ICR unit.

Apply V_{PD} bias to photo diodes as defined in Table 2.

Apply V_{CC} bias to TIAs as defined in Table 2.

Apply a bias to V_{MC} input to select AGC or MC mode operation.

Apply appropriate bias to V_{GC} or V_{OA} input to adjust the operating point of the TIA.

The voltage output at the peak detect pin, V_{PK} , can be monitored to ascertain the Gain control point.

The RF output from the ICR unit can be monitored at any of the four differential channels.

To Power down, this sequence should be used:

The ICR unit can be powered down following the sequence described below

Turn the TIA bias, V_{CC} , to zero volts.

Turn the control voltages (V_{OA} and V_{GC}) to TIA to zero volts.

Turn the PD bias, V_{PD} , to zero volts.

Before disconnecting the ICR Unit from the power supplies, all the supplies should be turned off to avoid any voltage spike to the unit.

4. Evaluation: experimental Set-up

The test setup is sketched in figure (4); it reproduces a real system for frequency dissemination. The optical apparatus for the noise cancellation is now described in detail in figure 4(a). It consists in a fiber-based Michelson interferometer where an original light is sent to a remote lab and partially reflected back; this allows detection of the round-trip phase noise and its compensation; two Faraday mirrors (FM1, FM2) are used to compensate for birefringence effects on the round-trip light. A couple of AOMs, with a working frequency around 40MHz, is exploited to avoid spurious interferences at the detection generated from backreflections along the fiber path. Using Direct Digital Synthesizers (DDS) AOM(+) is set to 41MHz while AOM(-) is set to 40MHz. The two are chosen with opposite sign to obtain an overall shift of 1 MHz on the output beam; the reason for that will be explained later. Accordingly, the round-trip signal is shifted by 2MHz, and this is as well the frequency of the beatnote used to compensate the fiber noise. After a 10MHz low pass filter, the beatnote signal is upconverted to 160MHz by means of an electronic mixer (MX1) driven by a DDS set to 158MHz. In this way, it can be filtered by a dedicated narrow-band filter (PBF) at 160MHz and then divided by a factor 160 with a prescaler. This operation scales down the phase noise by the same factor, hence producing smaller variations of the phase-error signal detected on MX2; in turns, this ensures the linearity of the feedback loop. The LO signal used for the phase detection is derived from a H-maser. The error signal is then integrated and feeds AOM(+) through a Proportional-Integral loop driving a DDS. The latter constantly updates its frequency value according to the error signal received by the PID. The *deviation* parameter of the DDS sets the proportionality factor between the error signal and the frequency correction. This parameter must be properly set to keep the loop effective yet far from auto-oscillations. If the deviation value is too large, the loop oscillates otherwise for a too small deviation, the cancellation of the phase noise is not achieved.

An important aspect of this test setup is that it is meant to analyze the effect of birefringence in an optical link. These phenomena can be replicated even over a very short link using special devices called *polarization controllers* (PCON). These objects can convert any input

polarization state to any output polarization state selectable by the application of a certain voltage. This is possible thanks to the cascaded electro-optical plates which convert the electric stimulus to a proportional change of the birefringence value Δn . The model adopted in our setup is the **BATi Acrobat PCM410** whose construction is shown in figure 4(b). It is made by four electro-optic plates at different orientations driven by four independent voltage inputs. However this device is not expected to introduce a pure birefringence change but also an undesired OPL variation. This two effects can be confused during the DSP analysis; however, the activation of the phase noise cancellation circuit presented above suppresses the second effect, ensuring that only birefringence phenomena survive. In our tests, we stimulate the PCON in only one channel at a time using different functions generated by a DDS.

The beam is properly subjected to the polarization set and the polarization check stages before the injection in the fiber branch connected to the PCON. At the receiving station the regeneration laser is replaced by a "pseudo oscillator" ("LO" in figure (4)) which simply consists in the direct laser source itself. This allows a direct measurement of the phase acquired while passing into the link, and is insensitive to the source phase noise itself, as this term is common between the two arms that interfere on the DPOH. The direct connection adopts a PM fiber in order to maintain a linear polarization until the DPOH input port.

The DPOH adopted in these tests is the **Neophotonics MICRO-ICR** mounted on a **GEN-IV Evaluation Board** which controls the settings of the TIAs used in the first amplification stage of the four channels. The outputs are thus read-out by a Lecroy WaveSurfer-104X real time oscilloscope.

(a)

(b)

Figure 4: (a) The optical link setup with electronics for noise cancellation. (b) inside-view of the polarization controller (PCON) BATi Acrobat PCM410 with four waveplates at different orientations and the corresponding control signals $V1 \div V4$

5. Results of the DSP

The two signals compared in the DPOH have different frequencies, as E_{out} travels through the two AOMs and is thus frequency shifted by 1MHz as compared to the original laser, which is sent directly to the LO port of the DPOH. Heterodyne detection is employed for two reasons. The first is a technical one, and is due to the fact that the PLL for noise cancellation acts on an acousto-optic modulator where the transmitted frequency is changed in opposition to the fiber-induced noise: as these devices operate at a fixed central frequency, the transmitted source is necessarily shifted with respect to the original one. The second reason

is more fundamental and is due to the fact that photodiodes are always affected by flicker noise at Fourier frequencies lower than about 100kHz: hence, moving the detected signal from dc to the RF spectrum often ensures better signal to noise ratio. Detecting the signal at 1 MHz poses some constraints on the maximum data acquisition length: the total storing capacity of the WaveSurfer-104X that records the values of the four DPOH channels is 10 MS which implies, in a 4-channels configuration a maximum acquisition length per channel equal to 2.5 MS. In addition, the adopted sampling frequency must be high enough to fulfill the Nyquist sampling theorem and avoid aliasing. On the other hand, a too high sampling rate would limit the data acquisition length due to the finite memory of the oscilloscope. Therefore we choose a sampling frequency of 2.5MHz, i.e. a value as close as possible to the Nyquist frequency (that is 2MHz for a 1MHz signal). With these parameters the total time of the single acquisition is 1s. The four DPOH channels readings are stored and post-processed via software; as a first step, the digital values are downconverted by a digital multiplication followed by a low-pass filtering stage that fulfills two tasks: firstly, it rejects the sum-frequency signal obtained at the output of the digital multiplication; secondly, it reduces the high-frequency noise, allowing to successively downsample the data in agreement with the Nyquist criterion, without introducing aliasing. And then, the sequences are downsampled of a factor 4, in order to speed up the DSP computation time, and therefore rounded to a total length of 600000 samples, The resulting dc signals are then passed to the DSP software which recovers the set of value $[\delta, \theta, \varphi]$.

In order to analyze the output of the algorithm three types of acquisitions are performed:

- *modulation OFF / cancellation ON (modOFF-cancON)*: this corresponds to the case in which the modulation of the PCON is turned off and consequently no induced changes in polarization occur, except for the natural and generally slow ones induced by environmental temperature variations. The feedback circuit for phase noise cancellation is activated as it should be in real operating conditions. In this case, a typical set of DPOH channels is like that of figure (5). It is important to stress that the data in the plots have been converted to dc, therefore they contain only the phase information, albeit mixed in a non-readily deducible way with birefringence-induced phases. We stress that traditional detection is equivalent to using one single channel out of the four. On the contrary, DPOH associated with DSP enables to extract more information combining the readings of the four channels synchronously acquired. The

DSP-recovered phase experiences about a 2π evolution within the acquisition time of 1s although it would be expected to be negligible, since the link noise compensation is activated. The reason of this fact lies in the inaccuracy of the internal quartz oscillator used by the oscilloscope as frequency reference. This was confirmed recording and analyzing on the oscilloscope the 10 MHz signal derived by a H-maser. A frequency discrepancy of $\approx 0.6\text{Hz}$ was found, corresponding to a relative inaccuracy of 6×10^{-8} , which is over 5 orders of magnitude worse than the 10 MHz test-signal accuracy; this was then attributed to the quartz and in fact it is compatible with the reported specifications for this device. This is also compatible with the phase trend observed.

Figure 5: Outputs of the DPOH after digital down-conversion and down-sampling in a modOFF-corrON configuration. In-phase and quadrature-phase signals on the two polarization axes \hat{x} (left side) and \hat{y} (right side)

- *modulation ON / cancellation ON (modON-cancON)*: this is the standard testing configuration in which, respect to the previous one, also the modulation of the PCON is activated. Considering for example a square wave modulation, the downconverted DPOH channels become similar to that shown in figure (4.5) where the PIPN effect is clearly visible. The output expected by the DSP is thus expected to separate this unwanted additional phase from the real metrological phase φ .
- *modulation ON / cancellation OFF (modON-cancOFF)*: this is the open-loop configuration where the phase noise cancellation is inactive. This acquisition is meant for comparison reasons only. In particular it is used to estimate the amount of environmental noise afflicting the system.

Figure 5: Outputs of the DPOH after digital down-conversion and down-sampling when the PCON modulation is turned on. In-phase and quadrature-phase signals on the two polarization axes \hat{x} (left side) and \hat{y} (right side)

We tested different waveforms for the PCON modulation. The first was a square wave that represents a fast transient event. Figure 6 illustrates the case of a modulation with a square-wave modulation of 10Hz frequency and 0.6V amplitude. The DSP recovery is executed in the three configuration described above (modOFF-cancON, modON-cancOFF, modON-cancON). Figure 6(a) compares the phase noise spectra of the retrieved φ which is the parameter of major interest. The phase noise spectrum in the configuration modOFF-cancON represents the floor noise that affects the system. This is therefore the target spectrum which is expected to be retrieved by the DSP even when polarization changes occur. It shows a typical f^{-2} trend with some peaks at 20Hz and 50Hz. The former is attributed to acoustic noise induced by the air conditioning system, as was previously observed also within different experiments performed in the same laboratory; the latter is rather common in low-noise electronic measurements and is due to the AC power line cycles. As expected, the phase noise spectrum of the configuration modON-cancOFF shows high power peaks at the frequencies of the modulation applied (10Hz and the odd multiples). This shows that the PCON does not introduce a pure birefringence variation. It is thus important to activate the noise cancellation loop, to compensate for the isotropic phase variations. The DSP performance can then be assessed in the operative condition modON-cancON. Figure 6(b) shows a chunk of the parameters sequence $\{\delta, \theta, \varphi\}$ recovered by the algorithm. δ and θ follow a square-wave modulation synchronous with the PCON driving signal. This is an expected result considering that these are the two parameter which model the birefringence in the adopted Jones model. The metrological phase φ has no signature of this modulation

and only shows a linear trend, which is due to a non-perfect compensation of the quartz inaccuracy with a slope comparable to that of the non-modulated configuration. This fact is verified also observing that the phase noise spectra of the modON-corrON configuration which overlaps to the modOFF-modON configuration settling below 10^{-5} rad²/Hz.

This is an important result, as it shows that the developed algorithm properly performs its task, separating the phase-information from birefringence. It is thus possible to extract the metrological phase even in occurrence of polarization changes where the standard detection method could not be adopted due to beatnote fading, and would not in any case be able to reject PIPN. The spikes synchronous with the PCON modulation transients observed on φ are compatible with the pulse-response function of the adopted electronic loop which has a bandwidth of about 3 kHz, therefore even though the round-trip signal is insensitive to polarization changes thanks to the Faraday mirrors, a square wave modulation is still present on it, due to the non-ideality of the PCON which does not introduce a pure birefringence, but also an isotropic phase modulation.

Several other acquisitions have been collected changing the modulation waveform and the used PCON channel, to assess the repeatability of the DSP behaviour in different experimental conditions. Figure 7 (first line) represents a square-wave of 10Hz causing large amplitude modulations on all channel signals. Figures 7 (second and third line) show instead sine-wave and triangle-wave modulations. In all cases, no signature of the PCON modulation is present on the DSP-retrieve phase, and the phase is still compatible with the unperturbed case. No spikes at the PCON modulation frequency are present, indicating that PIPN is effectively rejected from the recovered phase at the noise floor level.

However the DSP has not performed as expected in all the tested configurations. In particular it has been observed that for higher amplitude modulations or biased waveform, the PCON stimulus still affects the retrieved φ . This is shown for instance in figure 7 (fourth line) where the power density peak at 10Hz is more than two orders of magnitude larger than expected. Different aspects of the set-up have been investigated in order to overcome this problem. In particular, it has been observed that if the actual input polarization is even slightly different (fractions of radians) from that assumed in the model, the DSP can fail. This was checked with simulations and confirmed by experimental analysis. Based on this, particular care was put in the polarization set procedure; furthermore the standard single-mode optical fiber connections from the laser to the polarization setting stage have been

replaced with PM fibers to ensure a better stability of the launched polarization state during the acquisition and minimize possible long-term drifts. Still, these improvements did not lead to a full reproducibility of the DSP behaviour. A further object of investigation will focus on the PCON response which is suspected to introduce non-linear effects and the comparison or its replacement with different polarization controllers.

(a) Comparison on the retrieved φ in the three configurations

(b) DSP-retrieved parameters in the modON-corrON configuration

Figure 6: Recovered data for a square wave modulation of 10 Hz frequency and 0.6 V amplitude

Figure 7: Left column: DSP retrieved parameters. Right column: power spectral density spectra comparison

References

1. Clivati, C et al., "Robust optical frequency dissemination with a dual-polarization coherent receiver", 28, 8494-8511 (2020)

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